

A SEMIANALYTICAL FINITE ELEMENT METHOD FOR THE ANALYSIS OF FUNCTIONALLY GRADED CIRCULAR PLATES

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Heading

Motivation:

3D analytical approaches

The state space, pagano, power series, perturbation methods, etc.

Limitations:

(a) feasible for the structures with fully simply-supported boundary conditions only.

(b) feasible for the structures made of isotropic, transverse isotropic, and orthotropic materials, rather than monoclinic and general anisotropic ones.

3D numerical approaches

The finite element, meshless, differential quadrature (DQ), Rayleigh-Ritz, etc.

Weaknesses:

(a) very time-consuming

(b) computational inefficiency

A compromise between these two above-mentioned approaches is thus needed

Reissner's mixed variation theorem

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_R = & \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^R [\sigma_r \varepsilon_r + \sigma_\theta \varepsilon_\theta + \sigma_z \varepsilon_z + \tau_{rz} \gamma_{rz} + \tau_{\theta z} \gamma_{\theta z} + \tau_{r\theta} \gamma_{r\theta} - B(\sigma_{ij})] r dr d\theta dz \\ & - \iint_{\Omega^+} [\bar{q}_k^+(r, \theta) u_k^+(r, \theta, h/2)] r dr d\theta - \iint_{\Omega^-} [\bar{q}_k^-(r, \theta) u_k^-(r, \theta, -h/2)] r dr d\theta \\ & - \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \int_{\Gamma_\sigma} (\bar{t}_k u_k) d\Gamma dz - \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \int_{\Gamma_u} [(u_k - \bar{u}_k) t_k] d\Gamma dz, \end{aligned}$$

The Euler-Lagrange equations

$$\sum_{m=1}^{N_l} \sum_{e=1}^{N_e} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{I I}^{(e)} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{K}_{I III}^{(e)} & \mathbf{K}_{I IV}^{(e)} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{K}_{II III}^{(e)} & \mathbf{K}_{II IV}^{(e)} \\ \mathbf{K}_{III I}^{(e)} & \mathbf{K}_{III II}^{(e)} & \mathbf{K}_{III III}^{(e)} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{K}_{IV I}^{(e)} & \mathbf{K}_{IV II}^{(e)} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{K}_{IV IV}^{(e)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{u}}^{(e)} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{w}}^{(e)} \\ \tilde{\boldsymbol{\tau}}^{(e)} \\ \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^{(e)} \end{bmatrix} = \delta_{mN_l} \sum_{e=1}^{N_e} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}^{(m)}$$

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Fig. 1. The configuration and coordinate system of a circular plate

Fig. 2. The configurations of the (a) R4, (b)R8, and (c) R12 FAPM.

Fig. 2. The configurations of the (d) T3, (e) T6, and (f) T10 FAPM.

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Table 1 Convergence studies for variRMVT-based FAPM solutions of the displacement components induced in the plateaus.

Theories	h/R=0.05	h/R=0.1	h/R=0.15	h/R=0.2
Current T3 finite prism method (16x2)	5.1599	5.2086	5.2748	5.3645
Current T3 finite prism method (16x4)	5.5560	5.5971	5.6553	5.7355
Current T3 finite prism method (32x4)	5.5761	5.6113	5.6687	5.7482
Current T3 finite prism method (64x8)	5.6766	5.7117	5.7699	5.8513
Current R4 finite prism method (8x2)	5.7459	5.7808	5.8387	5.9195
Current R4 finite prism method (8x4)	5.7460	5.7808	5.8389	5.9201
Current R4 finite prism method (16x4)	5.7232	5.7584	5.8170	5.8987
Current R4 finite prism method (32x8)	5.7153	5.7508	5.8099	5.8924
Current T6 finite prism method (16x2)	5.7024	5.7408	5.8003	5.8830
Current T6 finite prism method (16x4)	5.7079	5.7466	5.8064	5.8894
Current T6 finite prism method (32x4)	5.7091	5.7449	5.8041	5.8868
Current T6 finite prism method (64x8)	5.7103	5.7457	5.8047	5.8874
Current Q8 finite prism method (16x2)	5.7440	5.7795	5.8385	5.9208
Current Q8 finite prism method (16x4)	5.7445	5.7803	5.8397	5.9227
Current Q8 finite prism method (32x4)	5.7234	5.7590	5.8182	5.9009
Current Q8 finite prism method (64x8)	5.7157	5.7510	5.8100	5.8927
Current T10 finite prism method (8x2)	5.7088	5.7444	5.8037	5.8865
Current T10 finite prism method (8x4)	5.7090	5.7445	5.8038	5.8866
Current T10 finite prism method (16x4)	5.7101	5.7455	5.8046	5.8872
Current T10 finite prism method (32x8)	5.7106	5.7459	5.8048	5.8875
Current C12 finite prism method (8x2)	5.7088	5.7444	5.8037	5.8866
Current C12 finite prism method (8x4)	5.7100	5.7455	5.8046	5.8873
Current C12 finite prism method (16x4)	5.7104	5.7457	5.8047	5.8873
Current C12 finite prism method (32x8)	5.7107	5.7459	5.8048	5.8875
CPT (Reddy et al. 1999)	5.700	5.700	5.700	5.700
FSDT (Reddy et al. 1999)	5.714	5.756	5.826	5.925
TSDT (Saidi et al. 2009)	5.7133	5.7546	5.8232	5.9194
3D solutions (Wang et al. 2010)	5.710	5.745	5.804	5.886

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Fig. 3 Through-thickness distributions of (a) in-plane stress component, (b) transverse shear stress component, and (c) transverse normal stress component, induced in a clamped, bi-directional power-law-type FG circular plate.

Concluding Remarks

A weak-form formulation of various RMVT-based FAPM to investigate the static behavior of bi-directional Power-law-type FG circular plates with simply-supported and clamped edges under mechanical loads.

Implementation of these FAPM shows their solutions closely agree with each other and that these solutions are in excellent agreement with the 3D exact solutions available in the literature.

The results show that distributions of the in-plane and transverse stress components appear to be much higher-order polynomial functions through the thickness direction, and these variables change drastically along the thickness direction when the material-property gradient indices become greater. These observations are helpful for making the kinematic and kinetic assumptions a priori when an advanced or refined plate theory for nonhomogeneous circular plates is to be developed.